

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**DYSLIPIDEMIA IN WOMEN WITH PREGNANCY INDUCED
HYPERTENSION****¹ Dr. Naila Khurshid, ² Major General Khurshid Muhammad Uttra, ³ Dr. Bikha Ram Devrajani, ^{4*} Dr. Syed Zulfiquar Ali Shah**¹ Assistant Professor Gynecology and Obstetrics Foundation University Medical College, Fauji Foundation Hospital Rawalpindi² Professor of Medicine, Army Medical College, Rawalpindi³ Professor of Medicine and Vice Chancellor LUMHS Jamshoro⁴ Assistant Professor Department of Medicine LUMHS Jamshoro**Abstract****Objective:** To determine the frequency of dyslipidemia in women with pregnancy induced hypertension.**Patients And Methods:** The pregnant ladies with hypertension visited at tertiary care hospital were evaluated and those patients who meet the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. The patients were taken randomly while the detail history was taken; relevant clinical examination and all routine investigations were performed. An informed consent was taken from every patient after full explanation of procedure. Every patient was advise for at least 12-14 hours overnight fasting and the 5ml venous blood sample were collected in a disposable syringe on next morning (before breakfast) for the serum lipid profile and fasting blood sugar (for the assessment of blood glucose level). The frequency / percentages (%) and means $\pm$ SD computed for study variables.**Results:** During six-month study period, total 50 ladies were evaluated for lipid profile. The mean $\pm$ SD for age of patients was 33.96 ± 5.72 whereas the frequency of dyslipidemia in pregnant ladies identified as 30 (60%) with mean BMI and fasting blood sugar (FBS) was 29.72 ± 2.52 (kg/m²) and 164 ± 9.64 (mg/dL). The DYSLIPIDEMIA was observed in 30 (60%) ladies with $\uparrow$ Triglyceride 07 (23.3%), $\uparrow$ cholesterol in 08 (26.6%), $\uparrow$ LDL 05 (16.6%), $\downarrow$ HDL in 02 (6.6%) and mixed dyslipidemia in 08 (26.6%) pregnant ladies with hypertension.**Conclusion:** The correlation of dyslipidaemia should be properly evaluated and treated to save the pregnant hypertensive ladies from complications.**Keywords:** Lipid profile and Dyslipidemia, Hypertension and Pregnancy.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Syed Zulfiquar Ali Shah**Email: zulfikar229@hotmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Naila Khurshid et al., *Dyslipidemia In Women With Pregnancy Induced Hypertension.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Pregnancy induced hypertension (PIH) creates in about 2% of pregnancies is as yet in charge of a huge extent of perinatal and maternal dreariness and mortality [1]. Current ideas of pathophysiology of PIH recommend endothelial cell damage and changed endothelial cell function assume a significant job [2]. The inadequately perfused placenta is the starting point of a humoral component that influences maternal foundational work, straightforwardly or in a roundabout way, by enacting endothelial cells with vascular damage [3]. The trademark pathologic insult found in uteroplacental area of patients with pre-eclampsia is a necrotizing arteriopathy comprising of fibrinoid putrefaction, gathering of froth cells or lipid-laden macrophages in decidua, fibroblast expansion, and a perivascular penetrate [4]. This injury has been named "intense atherosclerosis." Work in the field of cardiovascular research has demonstrated that serum lipids directly affect endothelial capacity and that irregular serum lipid profiles are related with endothelial brokenness [5]. In that capacity the potential job of strange lipid digestion in the beginning or articulation of pre-eclampsia is a subject of expanding interest. Lipid and lipoprotein levels experience alteration in pregnancy, probably to supply lipid supplements to the developing hatchling. Plasma centralizations of TG and cholesterol increment roughly 30% and half, individually. In spite of the fact that the nearness of hyperlipidemia has been reported in ordinary pregnancies, the greatness and essentialness of the lipid changes in pregnancies confounded by PIH has not been very much characterized [6]. Increments in plasma cholesterol, triglycerides and low thickness lipoprotein have been noted. The histopathological finding noted in the uterine winding conduits in patients with PIH may hypothetically be related with changes in serum lipid portion. In ladies with PIH, plasma free unsaturated fats and triglyceride fixations

climb significantly over those saw in typical pregnancy, and do as such well before the presence of clinical indications of the confusion. This investigation was attempted so as to assess the serum lipids changes in pregnancies confounded by hypertensive issue.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The pregnant women with hypertension visited at tertiary consideration healing facility were assessed and those patients who meet the incorporation criteria were enlisted in the investigation. The patients were taken arbitrarily while the detail history was taken; significant clinical examination and every normal examination were performed. An educated assent was taken from each patient after full clarification of strategy. Each patient was prompt for somewhere around 12-14 hours medium-term fasting and the 5ml venous blood test were gathered in a dispensable syringe on next morning (before breakfast) for the serum lipid profile and fasting glucose (for the evaluation of blood glucose level). The lipid profile was assessed by National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) Adult treatment panel III (ATP III) arrangement of lipid profile. The information was gathered on predesign proforma and after that entered, spared and dissected in SPSS rendition 17.00. The recurrence of dyslipidemia was assessed while the example was dictated by serum level for cholesterol, high thickness lipoprotein HDL-C, low thickness lipoprotein LDL-C and triglyceride.

RESULTS:

During six month study period, total 50 ladies were evaluated for lipid profile. The mean $\pm$ SD for age of patients was 33.96 ± 5.72 whereas the frequency of dyslipidemia in pregnant ladies identified as 30 (60%) with mean BMI 29.72 ± 2.52 (kg/m²). The pattern of disturbance in lipid profile of diabetic patients is shown in table 1.

TABLE 01: THE FREQUENCY AND PATTERN OF DYSLIPIDEMIA IN PREGNANCY INDUCED HYPERTENSION

DYSLIPIDEMIA	FREQUENCY (n=50)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Yes	30	60%
No	20	40%
PATTERN OF DYSLIPIDEMIA	N = 30	%
↑ Triglyceride	07	23.3%
↑ Cholesterol	08	26.6%
↑ LDL	05	16.6%
↓ HDL	02	6.6%
Mixed dyslipidemia	08	26.6%

DISCUSSION:

Preeclampsia is the development of hypertension with proteinuria, edema or both, after 20th week of gestation. On the off chance that pre-eclampsia advances without appropriate treatment patient may in the long run create eclamptic spasms [7]. PIH creates in about 2% of pregnancies is as yet in charge of a huge extent of perinatal and maternal dismalness and mortality. Various examinations were done on the lipid profile in pregnancy incited hypertension [8]. In our study 50 pregnant women with hypertension were contemplated and a critical fall in HDL-C and increment of triglycerides and aggregate cholesterol was found in our investigation. The outcomes were like the investigation directed by Jayanta De et al [9] on serum lipid profile in pregnancy prompted hypertension who found noteworthy ascent in the serum triglyceride level in pre-eclamptic patients. The guideline modulator of this hypertriglyceridemia is hyperoestrogenemia in pregnancy that actuates hepatic biosynthesis of endogenous triglycerides, which is conveyed by VLDL. Expanded TG levels results in endothelial brokenness and in pre-eclampsia gets kept in inclined vessels, causes age of little thick LDL and hypercoagulability. In our study there was a huge fall in HDL-C in pre-eclamptic cases. Estrogen is in charge of acceptance of TG and HDL-C yet in PIH there was a fall in estrogen levels when contrasted with typical pregnancy. The low dimension of HDL in pre-eclampsia is anyway a direct result of hypooestrogenemia as well as might be because of insulin obstruction. Likewise increment in absolute cholesterol in our investigation corresponds well with study led by Cekmen MB et al [10] who considered lipid profile, lipid peroxidation and Vitamin E in pregnancy prompted hypertension and found a huge ascent in all out cholesterol levels in pre-eclampsia when contrasted with ordinary pregnancy which was like different reports [11]. LDL-Cholesterol levels in

our investigation are not are expanded essentially in PIH than normotensive pregnant ladies. This is as opposed to numerous different examinations which demonstrated a huge rise of these two parameters [12]. In any case, in some different examinations they were affectionate that there was no huge modification in this cholesterol level. The present examination demonstrates that noteworthy ascent in triglycerides, add up to cholesterol, increment LDL and decline in HDL-C which is conceivable causative elements of pathogenesis of PIH. Consequently estimation of these parameters will help in early identification and better administration of preeclampsia which is imperative to enhance the maternal and fetal result of preeclampsia.

CONCLUSION:

The estimation of serum lipid profile can be utilized to keep the progressiveness of pregnancy actuated hypertension in vulnerable pregnant women. The huge ascent in triglycerides, add up to cholesterol, increment in LDL and decline in HDL-C which are conceivable causative variables of pathogenesis of PIH. Subsequently estimation of these parameters will help in early identification and better administration of pregnancy prompted hypertension which is imperative to enhance the maternal and fetal result of PIH.

REFERENCES:

1. Uotila J, Tuimala R, Aarnio T, Pyykkö K, Ahotupa M. Lipid peroxidation products, selenium-dependent glutathione peroxidase and vitamin E in normal pregnancy. *European Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*. 1991 Nov 26;42(2):95-100.
2. Catov JM, Bodnar LM, Kip KE, Hubel C, Ness RB, Harger G, Roberts JM. Early pregnancy lipid concentrations and spontaneous preterm

- birth. American journal of obstetrics and gynecology. 2007 Dec 1;197(6):610-e1.
3. Enquobahrie DA, Williams MA, Qiu C, Luthy DA. Early pregnancy lipid concentrations and the risk of gestational diabetes mellitus. Diabetes research and clinical practice. 2005 Nov 1;70(2):134-42.
 4. Hubel CA, Roberts JM, Taylor RN, Musci TJ, Rogers GM, McLaughlin MK. Lipid peroxidation in pregnancy: new perspectives on preeclampsia. American Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology. 1989 Oct 1;161(4):1025-34.
 5. Scifres CM, Catov JM, Simhan HN. The impact of maternal obesity and gestational weight gain on early and mid-pregnancy lipid profiles. Obesity. 2014 Mar;22(3):932-8.
 6. Butte NF. Carbohydrate and lipid metabolism in pregnancy: normal compared with gestational diabetes mellitus-. The American journal of clinical nutrition. 2000 May 1;71(5):1256S-61S.
 7. Walsh SW. Lipid peroxidation in pregnancy. Hypertension in pregnancy. 1994 Jan 1;13(1):1-32.
 8. Herrera E. Lipid metabolism in pregnancy and its consequences in the fetus and newborn. Endocrine. 2002 Oct 1;19(1):43-55.
 9. Jayanta De, Mukopadhyay AK, Saha PK. Study of serum serumlipid p profile in pregnancy induced hypertension. Clin Biochem.2006;21:165-68
 10. Cekmen MB, Erbagci AB, Balat A, Duman C, Maral H, Ergen K, et al. Plasma lipid and lipoprotein concentrations in pregnancy induced hypertension. Clinical biochemistry. 2003 Oct 1;36(7):575-8.
 11. Enquobahrie DA, Williams MA, Butler CL, Frederick IO, Miller RS, Luthy DA. Maternal plasma lipid concentrations in early pregnancy and risk of preeclampsia. American journal of hypertension. 2004 Jul 1;17(7):574-81.
 12. Herrera E, Ortega-Senovilla H. Disturbances in lipid metabolism in diabetic pregnancy—are these the cause of the problem?. Best practice & research Clinical endocrinology & metabolism. 2010 Aug 1;24(4):515-25.